

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF I-FLASH CARD IMPROVING THE MEMORY OF COMMON SURAHS OF FORM 2 SPECIAL NEEDS STUDENTS IN SMK KALUMPANG

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to see how successful the use I-Flash Card in helping students in the Special Education Program in the Islamic Education subject in memories and recital the verses memorized from the Al-Quran in common surahs. This research included a total of 2 students in special need as participants. The first step in action planning was to recognize students who struggle in memorizing and reciting memorized common surahs with minimal errors in pronunciation. This research also aims to ensure that students are not bored during the learning process and to encourage students to memorize the Quran's surah. This research was carried out using diverse teaching methods and resources by using Interactive Flash Card, a digital process that replaces the previous handmade cards (traditionally). Sentences are typed on a computer with using MS Word and the card's background are made colourful. Each card includes sentences that have been cut short based on the student's skill. The respondents were given a pre-test and post-test. The result of the study (post test) showed that 2 students were able to memorize the traditional surahs more effectively after the intervention. As a result using I-Flash Card in the classroom is successful in enhancing students' memorizing and reciting with minimal errors in pronunciation once it is introduced.

Keywords: Memorize, pique interest, digital process, slow learner

1. Introduction

The Qur'an which was sent to the Prophet Muhammad s.a.w. is the last book revealed by Allah s.w.t. the Qur'an was revealed as a guide and reference for Muslims worldwide. Although Muslims come from various races and backgrounds, they are able to read and understand the Qur'an written in Arabic. However, for the disabled, the approach to reading or memorizing requires help for this group to more easily understand the contents of the Qur'an. The rapid advancement of technology has now greatly helped these disabled people in their daily lives. The use of technology in Education helps teachers a lot to educate students with special needs

in school. Teachers use technology as a facilitator to build teaching aids that are more efficient and appropriate to students' problems.

Through studies involving students with special needs with learning difficulties. Pupils in this category need methods that are appropriate to their learning, especially in memorizing and remembering lessons. A learning disability is a neurological disorder. In simple terms, a learning disability results from a difference in the way a person's brain is "wired." Children with learning disabilities are as smart or smarter than their peers. But they may have difficulty reading, writing, spelling, reasoning, recalling and organizing information if left to figure things out by themselves or if taught in conventional ways.

Memorizing the Al-Quran is a need for all Muslims and should be passed down to all Muslim students, especially for students with special needs. However, special need takes so long time to memorize a surah in the Quran due their conditions. Children with special needs are often referred as "intellectually disabled" due to significant limitations both in intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior. Hence, children with intellectual disabilities have much more difficulty learning new things, understanding concepts, solving problem, concentrating and remembering than their peers (Harris, 2015).

2. Problem Statement

One of the weaknesses found is special need with learning disability are quite weak in memorizing the Al-Quran and this makes them to be easily bored and less interested in the Al-Quran. In addition, the other weakness of special need students is unclear pronunciation of certain verses in Surah Al-Asr and this makes them to feel ashamed and inferior. Long sentences made difficult for special need students to memorize some common surahs. In addition to learning problems, slow learning children also face behavioral problems. Problems slow learner child's behavior caused by the limitations of psychological skills, including a) a limited mechanical skills; b) low self-concept; c) an immature interpersonal relationships; d) communication problems; and e) an understanding of the social role that is not appropriate (Malik, Rehman and Hanif, 2012: 136).

Therefore, various ways and methods used to help the special need in solving such problem Due to this weakness the teachers as a facilitator decided to assist special need student in solving the problem. Through this approach, teachers and also special needs students are able to overcome the problem. This teaching and learning of teachers in the classroom was designed to be creative and innovative to attract the interest of special need students and make them love the Quran. Generally, this study is to see the effectiveness of I-flash card common surah to students with special needs with learning difficulties. The first objective was to identify the level of effectiveness of the I-Flash surah Al-Asr card for students to memorize and remember common surahs. The second objective is to see the effectiveness of students reciting verses in Surah Al-Asr with minimal errors while memorizing.

Therefore, the idea to help special need students in memorizing and reciting the memorised verses of common surahs with the minimal errors in pronunciation brought forth to the introduction of I-Flash Card. These cards aim to aid teachers and special need students to overcome their challenges.

3. Literature Review

Researchers will briefly discuss the findings relevant to the topic in order to support this study. In addition, this section will discuss opinions that emphasize the use of I-Flash card is appropriate in helping students with special needs with learning difficulties in memorizing surah Al-Asr. A study was conducted on the frequency of reading the Qur'an among the visually impaired. The findings of the study found that the frequency of reading the Qur'an brings significant results in determining the level of mastery of the visually impaired. In addition, in the same study, the emphasis on the use of teaching aids (BBM) greatly influenced the achievement of mastery of the Qur'an by OKUMP students. This provides space and opportunity for OKUMP students to play an active role in their learning as they can repeat the learning until they understand it (Ab. Halim Tamuri, 2010; Fatimah, 2013; A. Rahman et. Al. 2010). Indeed, the use of teaching aids for students with special needs will give a good impact to this group, including students with special needs with learning difficulties. There are several learning theories that help strengthen the argument that the use of scan cards can help in teaching and learning sessions.

3.1. Cognitive Learning Theory

According to this theory, Snowman and Biehler (2006) explain that adaptation is the process of creating a "good fit" between the students' conception of reality and the new experience the students encounter in a classroom. The teacher plays a major role in this adaptation, when they introduce a new experience to the special need students as the teacher can facilitate the assimilation of this new experience so that it fits into the special needs students existing scheme or the teacher may have to change the cognitive thinking of the special need students by changing an existing scheme to incorporate the new experience. This process is referred to as accommodation (Pressley & McCormack, 2007). The tendencies of organisation and adaptation are progressed through the special need students' interaction with their environment and Piaget believed that people have a desire to organize their schemes to achieve the best possible adaptation to their environment this process is referred to as equilibrium. During a person's search to achieve equilibrium they must find themselves in a state of disequilibrium, a perceived discrepancy between a person's existing scheme and a new experience (Snowman & Biehler, 2006). This concept outlines the need for the teacher to create cognitive conflict with the special need students through education in the pursuit towards equilibrium. Pressley and McCormack (2007) outline the process for the teacher to provide educational support in overcoming special need students' misconceptions.

3.2. Multiple Intelligences Development

According to Howard Gardner, intelligence is a combination of psychologist and biological characteristic that enables individual to solve problem or create product that are valued in one or more cultures. Rubado (2002) worked with a group of 17 middle school students who were having difficulty learning the general education curriculum and were at risk of failing, but were not being served by the traditional special education program. To meet their needs, she began integrating MI into her instructional practices and found that students naturally began to identify their intelligences. It was found that students, through the process of self-reflection, began to identify their areas of strength in the context of MI and were able to identify which intelligences would enhance their performance. Through the use of a self - evaluation rubric, the students, many of them with special needs, discovered that they were using all the intelligences effectively, depending on the situation and realized that they were better-rounded than they had initially believed.

3.3. Learning Through Behaviour

According to Thorndike (1949), teachers need to constantly assess students 'readiness' (psychomotor, cognitive and affective readiness). Teachers can use colourful stimuli to engage students. In addition, teachers can provide positive rewards or reinforcement as well as provide a conducive and ready learning environment for students to learn.

3.4. Media Learning (Flash Card)

The use of Flash cards in the teaching and learning of students with special needs is good and will make it easier for students to understand the lessons given by the teacher. History of flash card goes back to 1834. Favell Lee Bevan wrote a book called *Reading Disentangled*, which included illustrated cards that some credit as the first modern flashcards. The cards were used for reading instruction, primarily to teach children phonics. The cards had illustrations of words and the first letter of each word.

According to Arsyad (2011) a flashcard is a small card that contains a picture, text, or symbol that can remind or guide to something related to the picture. This media has attractive colours that can be made as a game so as to attract the interest of children to better understand the material presented. Pictures on flash cards are collected, among others, a series of animals, fruits, clothes, colours, shapes of figures and so on according to the level of development to be achieved. Flashcard media has a positive effect on recognition, the implementation process of understanding the concept of numbers will make it easier for children to understand it more quickly through flashcard learning. This is supported by Ratnawati in Susanto (2011), stating that flashcard media can stimulate children to recognize numbers more quickly, making children's interest stronger in mastering number concepts and stimulating children's intelligence and memory. The use of flashcard media in addition to introducing numbers more quickly, children can also explore using these cards so as to stimulate various aspects that exist in children.

3.5. Slow Learner

Slow learners are a group of learning disabilities (LD) children who are being unable to learn which consists of mild cognitive disabilities, incapable to learn something in the amount of time assigned for the actual learning. Slow learners are having limited cognitive capacity or low in intelligent quotient (IQ), information processing weakness, poor in memory or short-term memory ability, lack of concentration with short attention span, having difficulty in abstract thinking which leads to inability to express ideas and deprived of attention abilities. Slow learners is a term that is sometimes used for low ability students, with IQ between 70 and 85. These individuals make up approximately 14.1% of the population, larger than the group of children with learning disabilities, intellectual disabilities and autism combined.

According to Chauhan (2011), Malik (2009), and Shaw (2010), a slow learner child having an IQ in between 76 and 89 with slightly differ from the normal children and limited ability in solving problem. They grasp the skills and concept even slower that is expected for children in general. The slow learner are mostly identified as low ability in reasoning on particular situation as well as to deal with abstract and symbols, such as in languages, numbers and concepts (Chauhan, 2011). Their limitation has also giving a great impact in dealing with complex problems and learning. This has leads slow learners to the situation of 'backward' performance in school who have very limited cognitive ability (Reddy, Ramar, & Kusuma, 1997).

4. Methodology

This study is a study on the effectiveness of the use of I-Flash Card in common chapters for Islamic Education subjects. This study emphasizes on the pronunciation and memorization of students with special needs. This study was conducted qualitatively in the form of observations and checklists. Abdul Sukor Shaari et al (2011) in his study described that the use of case study design using qualitative data is suitable for use when a study involving the observation of an individual or unit and a group of people. The target of this study is to consist of form two Muslim students with learning difficulties at SMK Kalumpang. Hafazan is one of the parts contained in the field of Al-Quran. This field of Al-Quran has three parts that require students to master those parts. In addition to memorizing, students also need to read the Al-Quran correctly and understand the verses in selected surahs of the Al-Quran. Thus, through this approach, researchers take incentives to help students with special needs with learning difficulties to read, memorize and understand sentences read with the help of i-Flash cards.

This study uses a structured observation method in which the researcher will observe, listen, and record information based on the test to be performed. In this case the researcher will make observations of the student's behavior whether focused or not while the teacher conducts the test to be conducted. Accordingly structured observations were performed along with a brief checklist. This study involved only two students with special needs with learning difficulties. At the beginning of the study students will pre-test by reading the usual surah (Al-Asr) without using a scan card for a week. During the first week of the study the students will be interviewed by the teacher to see the level of knowledge of the students. During the week students will be called for 3 times for a session to read surah Al-Asr. As students read the surah a checklist will be made to see the level of students remembering the surah. The method used by the teacher during the pre -test is traditional by simply asking students to memorize the entire surah each time they are called to read the surah. In the second week of the study, teachers began to make interventions using the scan card method for surah Al-Asr. At the beginning the teacher uses the card as a teaching aid while in class for the subject of Education. The teacher will read and recite the scan card of surah Al-Asr using the card and followed by the student. Pupils will also be called 3 times to read the surah scan card in front of the teacher. The teacher's target in the second week of the study was to help students pronounce with minimal errors. The teacher will focus the student to pronounce the sentence correctly before remembering it. In the last week of the study, students will be called by the teacher with the scan card to remember the surah Al-Asr as a whole.

Case studies used in this study to help researchers on identifying the effectiveness of the use of flash cards in helping students with special needs to memorize and pronounce the memorized surahs with minimal errors. To obtain complete data as well, researchers collected data from various sources such as interviews and observations during the teaching and learning process took place to get a complete picture and gain a deeper understanding of a research. The population selected for the study was students with special needs who study in one of the schools in the district of Hulu Selangor. The special needs students are fourteen years old and once had the knowledge of recognizing the letters in the Al-Quran.

Data were obtained through observations and checklists between the researchers and the respondents involved. A total of two fourteen -year -old special needs students were involved in this study. The sample selection technique were done at simple random while the schools are selected based on logistical factors. In order to obtain data, continuous observations were conducted throughout the specified period. Observations were conducted as the face -to -face school session begins. Pre-tests were done to see the students' mastery of common surahs and recognize the letters of the Quran. The research process took three

weeks in teaching and learning sessions in the classroom. During the observation process, the researcher also looked at the character of students with special needs as a whole.

The use of diagnostic tests was to measure the level of mastery of students during the pre -test as well as after the intervention was performed. The question paper contains filling in the blanks by writing the answers based on the sentence order from the selected surah. Pupils were given answers randomly and in sentence order. Each blank space provided by students were given two marks. Question papers were administrated after the intervention and each student's mistakes were assessed and recorded.

The surah scan card design is a scan card that has been innovated by researchers using MS word to build the scan card. The scan card used in this study involved surah Al-Asr. This surah has 3 verses that are quite long and it is difficult for students with special needs to memorize and recite. Therefore, the surah will be divided into twelve verse cutout cards. Each verse in surah Al-Asr will be cut or divided to make it easier for students to memorize and recite in minimal mistakes. The scan card will represent a single sentence that will make it easier for students to read and memorize. In addition, this scan card is mobile and easy for students to read and memorize the scan card. This scan card is half the size of an A4. This scan card usage manual, the teacher can show the scan card one by one to the students. Teachers need to make sure students to correctly pronounce each scan card of the surah. The teacher can also show the next card when the teacher is satisfied with the student's pronunciation. The teacher can use this during the session to correct the student's pronunciation in the reading of the surah. To attract the interest of students, the use of color in distinguishing each sentence is very helpful for students with special needs with learning difficulties. Flashcards system would be an excellent example for repetitive instruction as flashcards have been suggested as an easy way to teach students discrete skills (Cravalho et al., 2014).

5. Finding and Discussion

The results of a study for three weeks to see the effectiveness of the use of i-flash card surah Al-Asr has shown good results. Information before the study made by the teacher has identified the level of knowledge of students about the recitation of the Qur'an. Through the interview, the teacher found that these two students had the experience of hearing and reading the surah. However, the teacher found that there were many errors in pronunciation and sentence order that did not follow the sequence in the reading. In the first week of the study, the teacher asked the students to recite surah Al-Asr in the form of a long verse. The first time pupil K could not read the surah compared to pupil D. Pupil K was a bit confused with the letters in the surah. Pupil D can read well in the first sentence and is limited in the next sentence. The following is a table of the results of the checklist of student K and Student D during the study.

The table below shows the pre-test data that have been conducted without involving the use of I-Flash Card.

Table 1: Pre test result without I-Flash Card

Memorize	Student D	Student K
Sentence 1	1	1
Sentence 2	0	0
Sentence 3	0	0

Table 2: Pre test result without I-Flash Card

Pronouciation	Student D	Student K
Sentence 1	1	1
Sentence 2	1	0
Sentence 3	0	0

Based on the observation, Pupil K initially showed high confidence when asked to read the surah. However, when entering the second and subsequent sentences, the students' confidence began to fade and the students began to be confused with the letters and order of the verse. For pupil D the behavior is more careful in reading the surah and takes quite a long time to read the next verse. The careful attitude of pupil D was able to read up to the second sentence only and began to get confused for the next sentence. Based on observations regarding the behavior of students when they want to read a surah when called by the teacher. They often avoid reading first. Their efforts to give their best in reading the surah should be commended as they are diligent in reading it well.

Looking at the second week of the study, the teacher had used the surah scan card and the teacher's target at this point was to correct pronunciation errors with minimal errors. It turns out that through the intervention performed by the teacher, the results of the student study have shown a good improvement.

Table 3: Pronouciation result with I-Flash Card

Pronouciation	Student D	Student K
Card 1	1	1
Card 2	1	0
Card 3	0	0
Card 4	1	1
Card 5	1	0
Card 6	0	0
Card 7	0	0
Card 8	0	0
Card 9	0	0
Card 10	0	1
Card 11	1	0
Card 12	0	0

Based on the observation of students' behavior when the teacher gave the intervention by showing the scan card, students were seen to show interest in reading the surah. Pupils can easily make the most of the use of the scan card. In the second week, the teacher gives the students the opportunity to take home the scan card to practice memorization. Based on the observations conducted in the second week of the study the students were very interested in the design of the scan card. The clear writing and use of color on each of the scan cards attracted students to read. The shortened sentence division factor also helps students in reading with minimal errors.

In the final week of the study the teachers used scan cards to help the students to remember and pronounce with minimal errors better. Teachers have planned workstation themed lessons during the teaching sessions in the classroom. Students will be asked to move to each of the sentence cards and ask to say it with minimal mistakes. This activity was one of the methods used by the teachers during the last week's study. The results of the study showed that students got good scores for both parts.

Table 4 : Pre test result with I-Flash Card

Memorize	Student D	Student K
Card 1	1	1
Card 2	1	1
Card 3	1	1
Card 4	1	1
Card 5	0	1
Card 6	0	1
Card 7	1	0
Card 8	1	0
Card 9	1	0
Card 10	1	0
Card 11	0	0
Card 12	0	0

Table 5 : Pre test result with I-Flash Card

Pronouciation	Student D	Student K
Card 1	1	1
Card 2	1	1
Card 3	1	1
Card 4	1	1
Card 5	0	1
Card 6	0	0
Card 7	0	0
Card 8	1	0
Card 9	1	1
Card 10	1	1
Card 11	1	1
Card 12	1	1

Significant results can be seen to students after the use of scan cards that teachers use to students during teaching classes. Pupil D can almost memorize surah Al-Asr so well than before. While for student K also showed a good improvement from the next. Through the observations made in the last week, the students became confident in reciting and memorizing Surah Al-Asr well. These scan cards give good help to them in learning activities. While the teacher used this scan card, students K and D showed good interest and competition in pronouncing and memorizing better than their other peers. Thus, the use of this scan card

helps students with special needs with learning difficulties to learn and thus provide added value to their self-confidence.

Through the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of the use of i-flash common surah cards helps to improve students' skills in remembering and pronouncing minimal mistakes. There are several factors that drive the success of students in mastering these skills. Among the main factors is the role of teachers in planning good teaching and learning and appropriate to the needs of students. Planning in teaching and learning during the class contributes to the ability of students to learn. This argument can be further strengthened by Snowman and Biehler (2006) The teacher plays a major role in this adaptation, when they introduce a new experience to the special need students as the teacher can facilitate the assimilation of this new experience so that it fits into the special needs students existing scheme or the teacher may have to change the cognitive thinking of the special need students by changing an existing scheme to incorporate the new experience.

The second factor on the effectiveness of the use of this i-flash card is the nature of the scan card is designed according to the needs of students with special needs. The scan card design is easy to carry anywhere and can be used as material for flexible learning activities. In addition the cost to build this scan card is cheap and can be adjusted according to the level of the student. The division of sentences in each piece helps students to easily remember and pronounce. Problems slow learner child's behavior caused by the limitations of psychological skills, including a) a limited mechanical skills; b) low self-concept; c) an immature interpersonal relationships; d) communication problems; and e) an understanding of the social role that is not appropriate (Malik, Rehman and Hanif, 2012: 136).

6. Conclusion

Overall, the use of I-Flash card can improve the mastery of students with special needs in memorizing and pronouncing in minimal errors well. This research highlights several values that can be applied. The first is communication whereby students will be more daring to interact in memorizing the surah Al-Asr chosen by the teacher. In addition, the value of cooperation and mutual help between teachers and students or students with students. The next value is the students' self -confidence in memorizing and pronouncing with minimal mistakes increases.

The strength of the use of I-flash cards are teachers can use them as teaching aids during teaching sessions. Teachers can create activities in groups or in pairs as an innovation in the teaching of teachers, especially in Islamic Education subjects with children who have learning difficulties. Hopefully this method will be able to be applied to all schools that caters for Special Education Integration Programs in the subject of Islamic Education. Further research can be conducted to see the effectiveness of students with special needs in other common chapters.

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